

Security Oriented Nexus for Intelligent Commodity solutions marketplace.

PRESS RELEASE #2

SONIC Project Advances European Cyber-Resilience Through Strategic Partnerships and Community Engagement

Following its successful launch, the **SONIC Project** is proud to announce a series of strategic milestones aimed at strengthening the European Union's digital defences through collaborative innovation and active community integration.

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Strengthening the Ecosystem: Strategic Collaborations

SONIC is actively breaking down silos in cybersecurity research by forming high-impact partnerships with fellow EU-funded initiatives:

- ✓ **Cyber-Resilience Synergy Network (CRSN):** SONIC is a proud contributor to this powerful alliance alongside sister projects like VIGILANCE, CyberAid, ENFORCE, ACT4FOOD, 5G-TACTIC, and CTIS4NIS.
- ✓ **AIAGENT4CYBER - SONIC Partnership:** A specific strategic alignment has been established to harmonise SONIC's secure network architectures with AIAGENT4CYBER's agent-driven defence systems.

Expanding Footprint: Community Integration

To ensure long-term sustainability and interoperability, SONIC has integrated into premier European cybersecurity hubs:

- ✓ **ECSCI Membership:** SONIC has joined the **European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI)**, a network of over 35 EU-funded projects. The project contributes hardware-accelerated NIDS and malware analysis tools to this ecosystem.
- ✓ **Digital Skills and Jobs Platform:** The project is now an active member of the European Commission's Digital Skills and Jobs Platform, committing to closing the cybersecurity skills gap by sharing specialised knowledge and resources.

Recent Events

The SONIC team showcases its “Security-by-Design” vision at major professional and scientific forums, such as:

- ✓ **PCI 2026:** Presented by **Dr. Kitty Kioskli (trustilio)**, the project detailed its mission to the scientific community at the 29th Panhellenic Conference on Progress in Computing & Informatics in Athens.
- ✓ **FIRST Technical Colloquium:** Represented by **CYMPH**, SONIC actively participated in the “How cross-border incident response should be done in 2026” session contributing to the discussions of shaping the future of incident response.
- ✓ **DEP CYBER (UPTAKE) Gathering:** SONIC, presented by **trustilio**, took active part in this knowledge-exchange hub to align with fellow Digital Europe Programme (DEP) initiatives.

Stay Informed: Subscribe to Our Newsletter

As **SONIC** develops its **intelligent marketplace** for “easy-to-deploy” containerised cybersecurity tools, stakeholders are encouraged to stay connected.

Receive the latest updates on our research and joint results by subscribing to the **SONIC Newsletter**.

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